

Effect of Manpower Training and Development As A Policy Tools For Organizational Effectiveness: An Assessment Of Union Bank Nigeria Plc Lafia Branch

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ABSTRACT

Manpower is the total of number of personnel who are employed in an organization and available for a particular work. In organization. The manpower needed for a particular work in future is estimated and planned through different techniques organizational. While, training and development are means by which employees' productivity is enhanced and it is the responsibility of organizations to implement policy within its context. However, every training activity is aimed at accomplishing the dual function of utilizing and improving existing skills and techniques of operation.. The research tend to filled the gap where staff training and development are not carried out or they lack the quality that can improve the skills of employees and the ability to improve policy making process, which will negatively affect the outcome. The quality policy making is the product of sound training and development of staff, but much inadequacy is apparent in service establishments in union bank of Nigeria plc. While, the objectives includes: to examine the relationship between staff training, development and policy making .While, .the research hypotheses were formulated and used for testing the relevant data gathered from the administration of questionnaires. A combination of qualitative and quantitative method was used as its designed. and adopted, simple random technique. The techniques for data analysis was done in simple tables, under which analysis of each question were done and hypothesis were tested using the chi-square (x2) statistical method. The research finding includes: Staff training and development has impact on policy making and staff severally undergone training. Finally the research it revealed that trained workers perform better than untrained workers. the research recommend that : The organization should focused more on training junior staff and that most of the staff are not satisfied for this will decrease output. this therefore called for appropriate training and development programs for all categories of workers so that they will develop evenly to meet current challenges in the organization.

Keywords: Manpower, Training, Development, Organization and Policy.

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INTRODUCTION

Organizations “are agents of policy implementation and operate within the context of their service delivery or production and are saddled with power to make certain policies. Policy making is an integral feature of every organization which has been designed for specific goals.

However, policy making is an associated prerogative of only top level effective decision makers with functional experience and competent training.

Training and development are means by which employees’ productivity is enhanced (Collins, 2001). At the same time, top officials’ sensitivity and ability to formulate and respond to policies may receive momentum from training and development (Balogun, 1997). The irony of how training and development are handled in the public sector lies in the poor commitment to such programmed. In an age when corruption appears to have occupied a large proportion of government business, money allocated for training and development is either diverted and those given the opportunity for training are not considered. The fact that policies are prone to public criticism suggests that those who formulate policies and those who implement them should be revealed to regular training and development programmes as Daily’s work (2004) concludes.

Because of the whims and caprices exhibited by human beings, and in an Attempt to avoid domination by the mighty, policy making is inevitable as this ensures that people conduct themselves within a civilized frame of behavior. On the other hand, the process of training is ultimately aimed at coursing a significant increase and change in the ability of employees to contribute to the effectiveness of an establishment and laid down policies (Makinde, 2005)

Training is considered as pervasive management activity occurring within an organizational context. In many cases, however, every training activity is aimed at accomplishing the dual function of utilizing and improving existing skills and techniques of operating. However, to achieve success, training activities or practices must fulfill certain important conditions.

Employees must also fully understand and appreciate the reason for undergoing a certain training activity.

The Research Problem

Organizations are supposed to be the vehicles for bearing and implementing policies in order to realize latent objectives. Most organization pay lip service to training, others invest in training and development but hardly obtain value-returns in terms of relevant expectations.

Perhaps the attitude of employees to training and development is not tuned right. It may also be possible that employees fail to see any personal benefits from such training and development programmes. This is where the need for evaluation arises.

According to Collins, (2001) achieve the objectives of effective training and development; there is a need for proper staff development scheme and a well-designed plan of deploying staff appropriately. These features appear missing, inadequate funding constraint successful implementation of training and development plans of employees. Where staff training and development are not carried out employees’ ability to contributes or improve in policy making will be negatively affected and vice-versa as equally associated with Union Bank of Nigeria Plc.

The Research Objectives

1. To examine the relationship between staff training, development and policy making;
2. To ascertain the extent to which staff development has any impact on policy making.
3. To find out ways and means of establishing standard staff training and development schemes that would make for improved performance in terms of policy making.

Research Hypotheses

1. Ho1: Training and development of employees do not increase efficiency in policy making in the organization.
2. Ho2: Non-challant attitude of management officials to employees' training and development have not hindered employees' training and development has hindered employees' positive participation in policy making.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

Organizations are human creation. They are deliberately created to provide one form of service or the other to target human audience. Organizations would have remained rudderless if there were no effective management of the available human and non-human resources. By virtue of changes and technological developments in modern times, employees within an organization and the prospective ones who desire to join organizations need some form of training. Individual employees no doubt possess some knowledge, but training introduces them to the customized standards expected from the tasks they perform. Since every organization has set goals and objectives, individuals need to understand their role and functions within the organization's policy confines. Training and Manpower development are two interrelated sets of activities associated with the management of human resources. To understand the nature of these activities and appreciate their contribution to organizational performance, one would need to place them in perspective. First there is need to know what these activities entail. Second, there is need to have some knowledge of the range of factors. This would pave way for a discussion of the ways manpower training and development could be used as a tool for achieving these goals. And for these tools to be effective, they must be used appropriately.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Concept of Training and Development

Training can be seen as a process or a set of activities aimed at assisting an individual to acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for the effective performance of specific tasks or job. Within the context of work in modern business organizations, training is a continuous process which normally starts at the point of entry and progresses throughout the worker's career. In selecting the technique to be adopted, the profile of the workers or management for which it is designed and the type of needs it is, needs to be addressed. Staff training are geared towards the achievement of certain basic aims. According to Armstrong (1988), this aims are include: to shorten learning time so that new recruits reach their peak of efficiency as quickly as possible.

Manpower development is a much broader concept denoting the series of activities which an organization undertakes to secure for itself a regular supply of skilled manpower (human resources) to meet its present and future needs. The activities are also geared towards improving the performance for

existing staff, giving them opportunities for growth and development, and providing for smooth management succession within the organization.

While the concepts of staff training and manpower developments are closely interrelated, it is possible to identify a number of basic differences between the two. It should be borne in mind that these differences are a matter of degree. Three notable areas of differences are: objectives, time scale, and focus of responsibility. The objectives of training are relatively narrow focusing. As they were on enhancement of knowledge and skills either to rectify a recognized deficiency or to prepare individuals within the organization for new roles. The objectives of manpower development, on the other hand, are relatively broader. They are concerned more with improving the performance and long term goals of the organization;

Furthermore, while training activities is a set of activities easily allotted to a specialist (usually a training manager with the personnel management department) manpower development involves a much larger number of functional managers with responsibility lying ultimately with the chief executives (Armstrong, 1988).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Objectives of Manpower Training and Development

The main objectives of manpower training and development are to improve the qualities of the trainee, formulation of objectives for different needs and ways of achieving it. The training objective is very important because it determines the following:

1. The designed and content of the training programmes: Content of the training remain the same no matter the type of training involved.
2. It increased personnel efficiency, professional growth, smooth and more effective organizational performance
3. It improves the performance of existing employees (Armstrong, 1988)
4. To help people develop their capabilities so the company can meet most, if not all, its future requirement for managers supervisors, and higher grade professional, technical and sales or production staff within the organization.

Training

Training according to Oxford Advance Learner's Dictionary states that training is the process of preparing somebody or being prepared for job.

According to Cole, (2001) in his book personnel and Human Resource Management, training is a learning activity directed towards the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for the purpose of an occupation or task. The focus of training is the job for example, the need to have efficiency and safety in the operation of particular machines or equipment, or the need for an effective sales force to mention but a few.

The manpower services commission of the United Kingdom, which was set up by the 1973 Employment and Training Act defined training as a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behavior through learning experience to achieve effective performance in a range of activities. According to them, the purpose of training in the work situation is to develop the abilities of the individual and to satisfy the current and future of the organization. According to Armstrong (1996), expressing an

understanding should be developed and operated within an organization by appreciating learning theories and approaches it the training is to be well understood.

According to Krietner (1995), no matter how carefully job applicants are screened, typically a gap remains between what the employees sees and what they should know. An organization which desires to gain the competitive edge in its respective industry, needs among other things extensive and effective training of its human resources. Training is therefore a key element for improved organizational performance, it increases the level of individual and organizational performance. Casio (1989) put it this way “The economic and technological trends, the pace of innovation, change and development are growing faster year by year and as a result, provide clear signals that training and development are so relevant that both organizations and individual stakeholders must give a serious attention to.

Development

Development generally means the process of causing somebody or something to grow or making or becoming larger gradually. But in relation to manpower development can be seen as a process of increasing the quality or value or skill of an employee (personnel). From the definition, it can be sense that training facilitates manpower development and consequently organizational performance.

In the view of Chanokan (1987), manpower development refers broadly to the nature and direction of change induced in the employees as a result of educating and training programs. He says that development is managerial in nature and career focused. According to him, development is an educational process, utilizing a systematic organizational procedure by which a worker learns the conceptual and theoretical knowledge for effective pursuance of their responsibilities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Research design is aimed at systematically drawing up the procedural stages cum methods to be adopted in the investigation of a research problem. Thus every research follows a carefully mapped out plan. Hypotheses were formulated for testing with the relevant data gathered from the administration of questionnaires. A combination of qualitative and quantitative method was adopted.

Sampling Techniques

The sampling techniques, simple random sampling was adopted taking 50 people in Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, Lafia randomly out of total number of 100, people. However, where a research involve a large population. While, limitation cost, time accuracy and sometime the destructive nature of the measurement techniques necessitate sampling.

Source of Data Collection

The data used for this study were collected from both primary and secondary data sources.

Techniques of Data Analysis

All data collected were analyzed using simple tables and percentages. The techniques used was the statistical descriptive method, the overall response were ascertained and recorded with statistical tools like response, frequency, percentage, and total. The presentation was done in simple tables, under which analysis each question were done, and hypothesis were tested using the chi-square (χ^2) statistical method.

The sample of chi-square (χ^2) formular is $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_1 - E_1)^2}{e_1}$ where
 O=Observed frequency
 E = Expected frequency
 \sum = Summation

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	UN	SD	D	TOTAL
1.	There is relationship between staff development and policy making in Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, Lafia	30(28%)	25(21%)	10(8%)	10 (9%)	5(11%)	80
2.	Staff development has impact on policy making in Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, Lafia	35(28%)	25(21%)	10(8%)	5(9%)	5(11%)	80
3.	Not been considered for training can Decrease the Output of the organization	30(28%)	25(21%)	10(8%)	10 (9%)	5(11%)	80
4.	Staffs are been Undergone Training several times	40(28%)	20(21%)	10(8%)	5 (8%)	5(11%)	80
5.	Training Development Policy has been unbiasedly Applied to Workers.	6(28%)	8(21%)	2(8%)	20(9%)	5 (11%)	80
6.	Trained Workers Perform Better than Untrained Workers	30(28%)	25(21%)	10(8%)	10(9%)	5(11%)	80
7.	Do Workers Expect Promotion after Training	35(28%)	25(21%)	10(8%)	5 (9%)	5(11%)	80
	TOTAL	206	153	62	65	84	570

Degree of freedom = (R-I) (C-I)
 (7-1) (5-1)
 6 X 4 = 24

Table value at 24 and 5% margin error of level of significant = 36.4151

Calculated value of X^2 is 81.31 the table value at 5% and degree of 24 degree of freedom is 36.4151 the calculated value is greater than ($>$) the table value. Therefore we accept the null hypothesis (H_0) which state Training and development of employees do not increase efficiency in policy making in service establishments, and we reject the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which state that Training and development of employees increase efficiency in policy making in service establishments.

Test Of Hypothesis

H_0 : Training and development of employees do not increase efficiency in policy making in organization, and we reject the alternative hypothesis

H_1 : Training and development of employees increase efficiency in policy making in organization.

Research Findings

1. They are relationship between staff development and policy making in Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, Lafia
2. Staff development has impact on policy making in Union of Bank Nigeria Plc, Lafia
3. The findings reveled that not been considered for training can decrease the output of the organization
4. It also shows that staff development has impact on policy making in Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, Lafia
5. It shows that Staffs are been Undergone Training several times
6. Training and development policy has been unbiasedly applied to workers.
7. Finally, it revealed that trained of workers perform better than untrained workers.

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